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Videos in physics theory and laboratory teaching: usage and retention analytics

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ABSTRACT

This paper investigates students' video usage in physics studies and differences in viewer retention. The educational videos are produced by the physics teacher team in Tampere University of Applied Sciences. A large enough number of video views is needed to provide a representative overview of the usage and therefore, only those videos which had over 300 views were included in this study, resulting in 50 video clips. The retention patterns differ between video categories: laboratory work instruction videos are watched differently than homework solution videos and theory videos. They are rewound and played many times to find advice for specific needs in relation to using laboratory instruments. Homework solution videos, on the other hand, have a higher watching at the end suggesting that students check the correctness of their own calculations. Even though this is a case study in physics, other disciplines have similar needs for video material. Therefore, the authors believe that the results are generalizable also to other engineering subjects.

Conference Key Areas: Physics and Engineering Education, Open and Online Engineering Education, Engineering Education Research

Keywords: Physics, Educational videos, Retention, Analytics

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INTRODUCTION

Contemporary pedagogical trends emphasize students' active engagement. Students who studied using interactive engagement methods reached better conceptual understanding [1] and better learning outcomes [2] than students using traditional methods. Some best-known activating methods in physics are Peer Instruction [3], Interactive lecture demonstrations [4] and Flipped classroom [5]. In those methods students need to be prepared to enable effective and active working. This can be achieved with the help of online videos. To add interactivity to videos PlayPosit and other similar tools can be used to attach automated multiple choice or open ended questions to any video [6,7]. With video instruction, it is possible to intensify physics laboratory work and shorten the needed laboratory time [7]. In general, educational video clips save valuable face-to-face time in classroom teaching and they are a necessary component of online courses. There are studies which show that the student's video viewing activity and final grade in a course have a correlation [8]. Some studies also have investigated viewer retention and retention patterns [9]. Viewer retention (audience retention) measures the ability of a certain video clip to capture and hold audience's attention throughout the video. Therefore, viewer retention data can help guide improvements for next videos.

1 EDUCATIONAL VIDEOS AT TAMPERE UNIVERSITY OF APPLIED SCIENCES

Students favour short videos over hour-long lecture recordings [10, 11]. Therefore, in Tampere University of Applied Sciences physics teachers have chosen to produce short, one-topic video clips themselves, rather than record lectures. This far, they have more than 1200 videos. YouTube is used for video delivery and links to the videos are in course's Moodle platform. This way, it is possible to investigate the video usage both using YouTube analytics and Moodle's log files. In Tampere UAS, videos are used for four different purposes in physics teaching and learning: 1) Present theory of physical phenomena. 2) Show lecture demonstrations and measurements. 3) Present solutions to homework exercises. and 4) Instruct laboratory work.

A snapshot of each type of video is shown in Fig.1. At Tampere University of Applied Sciences, videos presenting physics theories are usually constructed using MS PowerPoint with some animations. The PP-slides are narrated by the teacher and converted to videos. This way, the graphical quality is good and modifications are easy to make. The drawback is that this method is rather time-consuming and depending on the number of animated objects on the slides it can take several hours to produce a 10-min video.

Lecture demonstrations and measurements are recorded with a camcorder or smart phone by a cameraman while the teacher carries out the actual demo or measurement explaining it simultaneously. The same applies to laboratory instruction videos. The proper handling of laboratory instruments can be presented as videos. Also, instructions for data analysis and scientific reporting can be provided with videos. In a previous study, it was shown that with the help of pre-laboratory video instruction it was possible to remarkably speed up student working in an elementary engineering physics laboratory course [7]. Also, the time spent in laboratory was shorter.

Solutions to homework exercises are calculated with a marker pen to paper and recorded from above (Fig. 2). The recording device can be almost any recorder, but smart phones and tablets are very suitable for this purpose. The teacher's propagation

speed is automatically similar to that of writing on blackboard. Therefore, it is easy for the students to follow this type of videos. Compared to mere written answer, this method provides the students with teacher's reasoning and explanation about the solution and its steps.

Fig. 1. In Tampere UAS, videos are used for four different purposes in physics teaching and learning: A) Present theory of physical phenomena, B) Show lecture demonstrations and measurements, C) Present solutions to homework exercises and D) Instruct laboratory work.

Short, individually streamable video clips have dramatically increased versatility and possibilities in teaching and studying over the last ten years. At Tampere University of Applied Sciences, the videos have been used in physics teaching since 2013. During this time, the main playback device has been PC-computers (91 % of watching), whereas tablets (5 %) and smart phones (4 %) form only a minority.

Fig. 2. Recording a homework solution video.

2 VIDEOS IN THIS STUDY

The physics team at Tampere University of Applied Sciences has this far recorded roughly 1100 short, educational video clips for physics teaching and learning. They have been watched 410 000 minutes and 125 000 times. This results in 114 views per video on average. However, the distribution of views is far from even. For this study, 50 such videos were chosen, which represented different categories and had 270 views at minimum. The authors believe that this number of views is enough to give a reliable average of viewer retention. A summary and characteristics of different types of videos included in this study are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Characteristics of videos in this study.

Type of video	Number of videos	Average length	Average number of views	Average percentage watched
Theory	9	6:28	437	60 %
Demonstration	2	1:34	358	80 %
Exercise	30	6:45	573	55 %
Laboratory	9	11:40	383	52 %

A more detailed picture of the videos is presented in Fig. 3. It shows the length distribution of the videos. Based on table 1 and figure 3, it can be noted that the theory and the exercise videos have similar lengths, whereas the laboratory instruction videos tend to be longer. The demonstration videos just show one specific physical phenomenon and are therefore the shortest.

Fig. 3. Length distribution of different types of videos.

3 VIEWER RETENTION DATA

3.1 Theory and demonstration videos

Viewer retention can be analysed in YouTube analytics video-wise. Figure 4A presents the retention as a function of video position for all theory videos. Every video has a notch in the beginning. This means that watchers shut down the video within a couple of seconds after opening it. Similar behaviour is seen in all retention curves. These videos are “unlisted” in YouTube meaning that they are not publicly visible. Therefore, all the activity comes via learning management system. Therefore, it is likely that the notch is caused by accidental openings of (wrong) video.

The shorter videos have higher retention percentages in general, but the shapes of the retention curves are rather similar irrespective of the video length. This typical shape is presented in Fig. 4B. It seems that watchers lose interest rather evenly and the curve goes slowly down throughout the video length.

Since there are only two demonstration videos, both very short, no generalizations can be made. The curves in Fig. 4C for demonstration videos both show some spikes. These videos were used to show measurements in an online course and the spikes represent time instants where the values can be read. It seems that students have rewound the video to retrieve the numerical values needed.

Fig. 4. A) Retention curves for theory videos. B) Typical shape, interpreted as an average of curves in part A. C) Retention curves for demonstration videos.

3.2 Homework solution videos

Figure 5 shows viewer retention for homework solution videos. Due to the large number of this type of videos included in this study, not all of them are presented. A characteristic feature is clearly visible even in this smaller data set – namely the rising spike at the end of the almost each video. In most cases these videos present algebraic solution and numerical answer to a homework problem. Reasoning and necessary steps are simultaneously explained by the teacher to cultivate students scientific thinking. Of course, students are encouraged to try to proceed as far as they can without watching the video for help. The spike at the end suggests that many students have actually managed to solve the problems and have watched only the last frames of the video to check the correctness of their own answers. To make this checking

easier, the students could be provided with an additional snapshot image of the end of the video. These could be presented in the course's learning management system, together with the links to YouTube videos.

Fig. 5. A) Retention curves for homework solution videos. B) Characteristic shape.

3.3 Laboratory instruction videos

Retention curves for laboratory instruction videos are presented in Fig. 6A. The shape differs remarkably from those of all other types of videos. There are certain time periods that have been watched much more than other parts of the video. The retention percentages even exceed 100 % which means that the viewers have rewound it back and watched again. The shape suggests that the students have been seeking instructions for some specific actions to cope with the laboratory instrument. They probably have watched the videos before laboratory time, as supposed to, but needed to recall some aspects during the laboratory measurements. Authors suggest that to this type of videos list of content could be added to YouTube. It would help the students to find the parts they are looking for. An exemplary image of this table of contents is in Fig. 7.

Fig. 6. A) Retention curves for the laboratory instruction videos. B) Typical shape, showing characteristics visible in part A.

Fig. 7. Table of contents in a YouTube video.

3.4 Retention vs length

Figure 7 show the average watched percentage of each video as a function of video length for all video types. Regardless of the type, the longer the video the lower the average watched percentage. This result is in accordance with the findings in the literature [10, 11]. A large, 6.9 million video views study by Kim et al. showed that video length was by far the most significant indicator of engagement [12]. Students also engaged less frequently with assessment problems that followed longer videos.

4 SUMMARY

Watcher retention patterns differ among the video types Theory videos are simply watched through and the retention curves down as video progresses. Homework solution videos, have a spike at the end telling that students watch the last frames to check their answers. For this purpose, the students could be provided with a snapshot image of the end of the video - together with the actual video, of course. Laboratory instruction videos are rewind and certain parts are watched several times. Authors suggest that to this type of videos a list of video content could be added in YouTube. It would help the students to find the parts they are looking for.

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